

listed in the computer printout of line frequencies. An off-resonance single frequency decoupling experiment showed that the multiplicities of these lines due to proton decoupling correspond to seven singlets (quaternary carbons), eight doublets (CH carbons), and one quarter (CH_3). The fifteen aromatic CH of the three benzene rings come as five doublets.

- (1)
 (2) 4''-Cl
 (3) 4''-OCH₃
 (4) 4''-CH₃
 (5) 3''-OCH₃, 4''-OH

The broadening of the methyl peak found in the range δ 9.0-10.8 ppm is most probably, due to coupling to ^{14}N nuclei. The signal which falls in the range 99.5-99.85 in all the compounds is assignable to the tertiary carbon atom of the oxadiazoline ring^a. The two ethylenic carbons α and β resonate at 110 and 115, respectively. Carbon- β is more deshielded than carbon- α as it experiences the mesomeric withdrawal of electrons by the isoxazole ring $\text{C}=\text{N}$ and hence resonates at lower field^a. The absorption due to C'_4 , which is part of the chromophore encompassing the isoxazole-ring double

TABLE I— ^{13}C NMR CHEMICAL SHIFTS (δ) OF ISOXAZOLYLOXADIAZOLINES (1-5)^a

Carbons	1	2	3	4	5
CH_3 (q)	9.00	10.65	9.63	9.45	9.18
3 (s)	161.20	161.25	161.00	161.29	161.50
5 (d)	99.70	98.29	99.85	99.69	98.50
α (d)	109.87	109.67	110.24	110.01	110.36
β (d)	115.20	115.73	114.32	111.60	115.62
3' (s)	155.50	155.35	155.00	155.72	155.11
4' (s)	135.50	136.00	135.80	135.00	135.42
5' (s)	158.00	158.52	158.05	158.93	158.45
Miscellaneous ^b	—	—	55.29	21.01	55.75
			(q, OMe)	(q, CH ₃)	(q, OMe)
	—	134.20	159.40	136.50	157.05
	—	(s, 4'')	(s, 4'')	(s, 4'')	(s, 3'')
	—	—	—	—	160.25
					(s, 4'')

^aOff-resonance multiplicities in parenthesis. ^bIncludes substituents on benzene ring in compounds 2-5.

bonds and styryl moiety, is at 135.5, found in all the compounds. The peak at 158 is due to C'_5 , which is flanked by ethylenic double bond and isoxazole ring oxygen. Assigning such a downfield absorption to this carbon is justified because it is also under the electron withdrawing influence of $\text{C}=\text{N}$ of the isoxazole. All the five compounds

show signal around 155 assignable, most probably, to C'_4 . The most downfield signal of the spectrum at 161.30 is due to C_3 , as it is an sp^3 carbon attached to two nitrogens in addition to a benzene ring.

The rest of the assignments are complicated by the presence of three aromatic rings which result in strong signals near 128 ppm which are not readily distinguished from one another.

Experimental

Instrument : Nucleus, ^{13}C ; frequency, 20 MHz, instrument, Varian FT-80A; mode, FT; lock, internal; temperature, 30°; solvent, (a) compounds 1-4 in CDCl_3 and (b) compound 5 in $\text{DMSO}-d_6$; concentration, 0.5 M; tube size, 10 mm o.d.; standard, TMS; pulse width, 5 μs ; acquisition time, 1.0 s; spectral width, 5 KHz; number of transients, 80 000 and 110 000; number of data point, 10 000, decoupling conditions, decoupling mode (1), decoupler off set (56); flip angle, 45°; repetition rate 1.0 s; digital resolution, 1.6 points/Hz; and resolution enhancement, sensitivity enhancement was employed, using a decreasing exponential weighting function with a time constant of 0.7 Hz, resulting in 0.45 Hz line broadening

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Prof. E. V. Sundaram, Head, Department of Chemistry and Dean, Faculty of Science, Kakatiya University, Warangal, for facilities and Dr. J. N. Shoolery for the spectra.

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Synthesis of 2-Aryl-4(1H)-anthryridinones

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Manuscript received 4 July 1985 accepted 24 December 1985

SCANTY information is available in literature concerning the chemistry of anthryridines¹⁻⁴. In the present communication, a series of hitherto unknown 2-aryl-4(1H)-anthryridinones are reported

Scheme 1

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF 2-ARYL-4(1H)-ANTHYRIDINONES (3)*

Sl no.	R	Yield %	Molecular formula	Analysis % Found/(Calcd)		
				C	H	N
1	Phenyl	65	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₂ O	74.70 (74.73)	4.05 (4.03)	15.31 (15.38)
2	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	80	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ N ₂ O	75.20 (75.26)	4.50 (4.53)	14.56 (14.63)
3.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	82	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₂	71.20 (71.29)	4.21 (4.29)	13.85 (13.86)
4	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	71	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂	70.52 (70.59)	3.75 (3.81)	14.59 (14.53)
5	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	75	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂	70.50 (70.59)	3.79 (3.81)	14.50 (14.53)
6.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	80	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ N ₂ OCl	66.35 (66.45)	3.22 (3.26)	13.63 (13.68)
7.	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	78	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ N ₂ OBr	57.99 (57.95)	2.85 (2.84)	11.91 (11.93)
8	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	65	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂	64.07 (64.15)	3.11 (3.14)	17.52 (17.61)
9.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	67	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂	64.04 (64.15)	3.11 (3.14)	17.55 (17.61)
10.	2-Hydroxy-4-chlorophenyl	70	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	63.19 (63.16)	3.05 (3.10)	13.09 (13.00)
11	2-Hydroxy-4-methylphenyl	72	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₂	71.21 (71.29)	4.25 (4.29)	13.95 (13.86)
12	α -Naphthyl	65	C ₂₁ H ₁₃ N ₂ O	77.94 (78.02)	4.00 (4.02)	13.05 (13.00)
13.	β -Naphthyl	66	C ₂₁ H ₁₃ N ₂ O	77.95 (78.02)	4.01 (4.02)	13.07 (13.00)
14.	2-Pyridyl	68	C ₁₈ H ₁₀ N ₄ O	70.00 (70.07)	3.61 (3.65)	20.57 (20.44)
15.	3-Pyridyl	70	C ₁₈ H ₁₀ N ₄ O	70.01 (70.07)	3.61 (3.65)	20.58 (20.44)
16.	4-Pyridyl	70	C ₁₈ H ₁₀ N ₄ O	7.00 (70.07)	3.61 (3.65)	20.57 (20.44)
17	2-Furyl	67	C ₁₈ H ₉ N ₂ O ₂	68.51 (68.44)	3.38 (3.42)	15.81 (15.97)
18	2-Thienyl	69	C ₁₈ H ₉ N ₂ OS	64.44 (64.52)	3.21 (3.23)	15.00 (15.05)

*All compounds have high m p. 300°.

The starting compound 2-amino-3-cyano-1,8-naphthyridine (1) was obtained by the condensation of 2-aminonicotinaldehyde with malonitrile in ethanol with piperidine as catalyst⁵. Condensation of 1 with aryl methyl ketones (2) in glacial acetic acid with a trace of concentrated sulphuric acid gave 2-aryl-4(1H)-anthryridinones (3) in good yield (Scheme 1). All the synthesised compounds were satisfactorily characterised by elemental analyses and ir spectral data. In the ir spectra, the absence of a characteristic strong band at 2200 cm⁻¹ indicated the absence of cyano group. 3 exhibited characteristic bands at 1680 (C=O) and 3300 cm⁻¹ (NH) and an intense band at 1600 cm⁻¹ (C=N). The spectra also exhibited bands at 1490, 1460, 1400, 1380, 1220, 1180, 1100, 900, 870 and 730 cm⁻¹. The pertinent data of the compounds thus prepared are recorded in Table 1.

Experimental

All the melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 283 spectrophotometer. The homogeneity and purity of the compounds were tested by tlc.

2-Amino-3-cyano-1,8-naphthyridine (1): It was prepared by the condensation of 2-aminonicotinaldehyde with malonitrile by the method of Hawes and Wibberley⁵ in 95% yield, m p. 261° (lit. 260-2°); ν_{max} (nujol) 3450, 3250, 2200, 1640, 1600, 1550, 1495, 1440, 1150, 1060 and 780 cm⁻¹.

2-Aryl-4(1H)-anthryridinones (3): A mixture of 1 (0.1 mol) and appropriate aryl methyl ketone (2, 0.1 mol) was refluxed in glacial acetic acid (30 ml) in the presence of a catalytic amount of concentrated sulphuric acid for 4 h. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool and poured onto crushed ice. The separated solid was filtered and recrystallised from aqueous acetic acid to give 3.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Prof E. V. Sundaram, Head, Department of Chemistry and Dean, Faculty of Science, Kakatia University, Warangal, for facilities. Two of the authors (K. V. R. and B. S.) thank U. G. C., New Delhi, for financial support and the others (K. R. R. and K. M.) thank C. S. I. R., New Delhi, for the award of Junior Research Fellowship and Pool Officer, respectively.

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Syntheses and Nucleophilic Additions to Conjugated Imines of 3-(2-Methoxyphenyl)-5-(4-aminophenyl)isoxazole and 1,2-Dihydro-5-acenaphthylenecarboxaldehyde

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Manuscript received 1 April 1985, revised 9 August 1985,
accepted 2 December 1985

AZOMETHINES are known to undergo addition reactions wherein a variety of reagents add on to the polarised double bond^{1,2}. In continuation of our earlier work, we have carried out syntheses of some imines by reacting 3-(2-methoxyphenyl)-5-(4-aminophenyl)isoxazole with aromatic aldehydes and reacting 1,2-dihydro-5-acenaphthylenecarboxaldehyde³ with aromatic amines. The imines 1-7 subsequently obtained gave good yields of cyanoimines (8-14) on treatment with potassium cyanide in the presence of traces of acetic acid. The imines (1-7) were also reduced to the dihydro products (15-21) with sodium borohydride.

Experimental

All melting points were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. The ir spectra were obtained in KBr pellets and the nmr spectrum in CDCl₃.

3-(2-Methoxyphenyl)-5-(4-aminophenyl)isoxazole 4'-Nitroflavone was synthesised by the reported procedure⁴. 4'-Nitroflavone was reacted with hydroxylamine hydrochloride to yield 3-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-5-(4-nitrophenyl)isoxazole (A) (70%), m.p. 230°. Alternately, (A) was also obtained by reacting 4'-nitro-2-hydroxydibenzoylmethane with hydroxylamine hydrochloride.

Compound (A) was then methylated by using dimethyl sulphate and refluxing with fused potassium carbonate in dry acetone to yield, 3-(2-methoxyphenyl)-5-(4-nitrophenyl)isoxazole (B) (60-65%), m.p. 174°.

Compound (B) was then reduced by using granulated tin and conc. hydrochloric acid to yield the amine 3-(2-methoxyphenyl)-5-(4-aminophenyl)isoxazole (50%), m.p. 137° (Found: C, 72.14; H, 5.28; N, 10.47. C₁₆H₁₄N₂O₂ requires: C, 72.18; H, 5.26; N, 10.52%); ν_{max} 1 626 (C=N of isoxazole ring), 1 054 (OCH₃) and 3 500 cm⁻¹ (NH of primary amine); δ 3.69 (2H, bs, NH₂), 3.94 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.9 (1H, s, C=CH of isoxazole), 6.75-7.9 (8H, m, ArH).

1,2-Dihydro-5-acenaphthylenecarboxaldehyde³; A mixture of acenaphthene, *N*-methylformanilide, phosphorous oxychloride in *o*-dichlorobenzene was reacted to yield the desired aldehyde.

TABLE I

Compd. no.	R	Molecular formula	M p. °C	Yield %	N% : Found/ (Calcd.)
1	2-Ph	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	174	85	7.49 (7.56)
2	4-NO ₂	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₄	137	60.5	10.43 (10.52)
3	4-OCH ₃	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂	134	70	7.18 (7.29)
4	H	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	91	65	7.84 (7.90)
5	4-NO ₂	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂	105	80	9.13 (9.27)
6	H	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N	98	60	5.36 (5.45)
7	4-Cl	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ NCl	103	70	4.68 (4.80)

Imines 1-7 (Table I): (i) The isoxazole amine (0.01 mol) was dissolved in ethanol, acidified by adding a few drops of acetic acid, and then various aromatic aldehydes (0.01 mol) were added. The mixture was refluxed for 2 h. The product (1-4) separated on cooling, was filtered and crystallised from ethanol. (ii) The acenaphthylenecarboxaldehyde (0.01 mol) was dissolved in ethanol containing a few drops of acetic acid. The mixture was refluxed for 2 h. The product (5-7) which separated on cooling was filtered and crystallised from ethanol. The ir spectrum (KBr) showed the absorption for CH=N at 1 668 cm⁻¹.